

Legume Hub background

The Legume Hub was developed in the *Legumes Translated* thematic network project which was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. The consortium was comprised of 17 partners in 9 countries with 14 local innovation groups.

Governance of the Legume Hub

The European Legume Hub Community collectively owns the Legume Hub. All users are encouraged to join the Hub Community by registering on the Legume Hub website.

The community has a board elected by its members. The elected board organises the review of contributions, develops policy on content, and guides the technical management of the Legume Hub.

Members of the board

- Donal Murphy-Bokern, Germany
- Leo Rittler, Donau Soja, Austria
- Christine Watson, Scotland's Rural College, United Kingdom
- Lauren Dietemann, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL, Switzerland
- Mato Mrkalj, NUTRIS.farm Ltd., Croatia
- Svetlana Balešević-Tubić, Seed Association of Serbia
- Kristina Petrović, BioSense Institute, Serbia

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Chairman of the Legume Hub Community

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More information

www.legumehub.eu

Social media: @LegumeHubEU

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Legume Hub

Europe's knowledge platform for legumes

www.legumehub.eu

The Legume Hub philosophy:

shared knowledge, shared ownership

The Hub is an open and validated self-publishing platform for authors. The purpose of the Legume Hub is to empower all interested in the development of legume crop production and use by providing access to validated knowledge. It is a platform dedicated to sharing knowledge and successful practices across value chains, from plant breeding, on-farm activities, through to processing and consumption.

Join us

All who have relevant practical or research-based expertise are invited to register and thereby join the Legume Hub Community.

Users include:

- Farmers as growers and users of legumes
- Breeders
- Processors for feed and food purposes
- Project consortia and teams, and
- All involved in the related parts of the value chains

Legume Hub members can publish articles or disseminate existing research reports, videos or photos. Contributors, their projects and organisations are given maximum recognition on the Legume Hub – each article is attributed to its author(s) and their organisations. Each is citable as a scientific or technical publication.

Content

The Legume Hub is a self-publishing platform for original articles, videos, images and viewpoints. Everything that is published through the Hub is subject to independent peer-review.

The Hub editors work to ensure that contributors can be proud of their input to the Hub and that the Hub is respected as a community of authors. Where copyright allows, members can also use it as a personal repository for existing publications.

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